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NERSC Technical Report no. 273

PREPARED UNDER THE
NORWEGIAN SPACE CENTRE
SATOC OCEAN WATER MASSES PROJECT

**Quality assessment of MERIS chlorophyll
Fluorescence Line Height (FLH) product
for the Skagerrak region**

by

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Bergen June 22, 2006

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REPORT

TITLE Quality assessment of MERIS chlorophyll Fluorescence Line Height (FLH) product for the Skagerrak region.	REPORT No. Technical report no. 273
CLIENT Norwegian Space Centre and NIVA	CONTRACT No. SatOcean Water Masses SatHav Vannmasser
CONTACT PERSONS Guro Dahle Strøm and Kai Sørensen (Water Masses, Project leader)	AVAILABILITY OPEN
AUTHORS Are Folkestad and Lasse H. Pettersson and Jo Høkedal (NIVA)	DATE June 22, 2006
SUMMARY <p><i>This study is performed under the Norwegian “SatOcean Watermasses” project in order to assess the Fluorescence line height (FLH) method for assessment of the phytoplankton abundance in Norwegian waters. Based on careful editing and quality control of atmospherically corrected spectral MERIS L2 data has been used to estimate the FLH signal. The FLH was compared with in situ observations and a linear relationship is found with an explained variance of about 75%, based on eight different days of observations.</i></p> <p><i>Interpretation of the FLH data together with the other information can reduce the number of false alarms of phytoplankton blooms from erroneously high Chl-a values obtained from the Algal 1 product. The FLH product is therefore an important additional source of information to improve the quantitative assessments in algae bloom detection and monitoring.</i></p>	
APPROVAL Lasse H. Pettersson	 Ola M. Johannessen, Director

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1. INTRODUCTION

Physical and biological conditions of the waters in Skagerrak can be monitored daily by both Earth Observation (EO) satellites (including the MERIS sensor onboard Envisat) and Ships of Opportunity (SOOP). Sun-induced chlorophyll fluorescence is a quantity related to the concentration and conditions of phytoplankton. This optical signal can be remotely estimated by the Fluorescence Line Height (FLH) product (Gower et al 1999). For the Envisat MERIS sensor this product may potentially improve the accuracy of chlorophyll *a* concentration (Chl-*a*) estimates, and thereby improve the quality of a service for algae bloom monitoring.

This activity is a part of the Norwegian Space Centre project “SatHav Vannmasser” (SatOcean Water Masses) concerning the harmful algal bloom (HAB) monitoring, disseminated at <http://HAB.nersc.no>. The objective is to investigate if the FLH signal can give additional information to improve the HAB-service, improving the service quality, by reduction of “false” alarms based on analysis of satellite Earth observations data. Conventional EO chlorophyll products have proven to be inadequate in optically complex (Case 2) waters often present in the Skagerrak region. However, even though the FLH product has been applied and validated for other regions (Gower et al 1999, Gower and King 2003, Gower et al 2003, Gower and Borstad 2004) little work has so far been done in order to document the validity of the FLH product for this region and European waters.

In this study atmospherically corrected MERIS spectral reflectance data are used to generate the FLH product in Skagerrak. The FLH product is compared to *in vitro* measured Chl-*a*, and the relation between the two quantities is investigated with regards to physical quantities and conditions, as well as to the quality of the MERIS L2 data.

2. DATA AND METHODS

2.1. MERIS DATA

MERIS Reduced Resolution (RR) Level 2 (L2) data were analyzed for a total of eight days in 2003 and 2004 (Table 1). These days were selected according to cloud free conditions along all or major parts of a ship of opportunity’s (SOOP) daytime transect in Skagerrak – between Oslo and Hirtshals (section 2.2). The MERIS data acquired in 2003 were re-processed in 2005 [First 2003 MERIS data archive reprocessing, PCF MERIS Team, Technical note, 2005. ESA], while data acquired in 2004 were processed by the standard ESA ground processor in near real time [Instrument Processing Facility (IPF) 4.10 – <http://earth.esa.int/pcs/envisat/meris/documentation/>], using a slightly different method for generation of the L2 atmospherically corrected products. However, the differences in data processing between 2003 and 2004 are not expected to have significant impact on the products relevant for this study.

Table 1: Dates of MERIS acquisition and SOOP data used in this study.

2003	2004
March 28	February 24
May 22	March 9
June 6	March 16
June 20	June 29

The FLH product was generated from L2 spectral surface reflectance using the BEAM FLH processor (BEAM version 3.0). Default settings were applied, including use of reflectance in bands 7, 8, and 9 (664, 680.5, and 708 nm center wavelength respectively), and a cloud correction factor of $k=1.005$. More information on the FLH processing can be found in BEAM's FLH/MCI Algorithm Specification, and FLH/MCI Processor Documentation, and in Gower et al. (1999).

For the eight MERIS images, values of all L2 products (including Case 1 water Chl-*a*, Case 2 water Chl-*a*, FLH, FLH slope and the value (0/1) of all 24 L2 flags) were extracted along the SOOP daytime transect. For correlation analyses between EO and SOOP products, data sampled north of 59.0°N were disregarded for reasons discussed in section 3.2.

2.2. SHIP OF OPPORTUNITY (SOOP) DATA

Continuous transects of temperature, salinity, *in vivo* fluorescence, and turbidity are sampled by NIVA's Ferrybox system [FerryBox project, Final Report, <http://www.ferrybox.org>] onboard the passenger ferry 'Color Festival' operating daily between Oslo (Norway) and Hirtshals (Denmark). Photosynthetically available radiation (PAR) above the sea surface is measured by a sensor on deck. For this study water samples were taken for laboratory analysis of turbidity and Chl-*a* concentrations. The Ferrybox data used in this study are partly from the EU FerryBox project.

For eight days in 2003 and 2004 with cloud free MERIS data and near synoptic Ferrybox data (Table 1), all the above-mentioned parameters along the daytime SOOP transect were extracted and analyzed. The maximum time difference between the Ferrybox measurements and the EO data was thereby seven hours. However, by disregarding MERIS data north of 59.0°N, the maximum time difference between SOOP and EO data is reduced to be less than four hours. The *in vitro* Chl-*a* sampled by the Ferrybox system has previously been found to correlate better with nighttime *in vivo* fluorescence than with daytime *in vivo* fluorescence (Sørensen, pers. comm.) Therefore, in addition to the data extracted along the daytime transects, *in vivo* fluorescence data along the nighttime transects was extracted to serve as a quality check of the *in vitro* Chl-*a*.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. HORIZONTAL FLH DISTRIBUTION

Images of the surface distribution of MERIS FLH in Skagerrak were generated (Figure 1). A high range of values – 0 to 0.0015 (dimension: per steradian) – was observed both within the whole dataset and within each image. Corresponding maps of the standard MERIS L2 chlorophyll products Algal 1 and Algal 2 representing Chl-*a* in Case 1 and Case 2 waters, respectively, were generated and compared visually with the FLH maps. The validity of the two Chl-*a* products was checked for all pixels in every image by the value of the corresponding L2 confidence flags (PCD 15 and PCD 17 for Case 1 and Case 2 Chl-*a*, respectively), which is set to either 0 (valid pixel) or 1 (invalid pixel). All images are presented in Appendix 1.

3.2. MERIS AND SOOP PRODUCTS ALONG THE SHIP TRANSECT

The MERIS FLH, Algal 1, and Algal 2 products along the SOOP daytime transect were compared to Chl-*a* determined from water samples (along daytime transect) and to the *in vivo* fluorescence (along night-time transect) (Figure 2). The FLH product is given in units of reflectance (sr^{-1}). Therefore, the

product is not directly comparable to Chl-*a*. However, one of the major goals of this study has been to investigate the relations between FLH and Chl-*a* for our region. The FLH data in Figure 2 were scaled to fit the observed Chl-*a* range. However, the scaling factor (i.e. the FLH:Chl ratio) can vary between images due to different light regimes, environmental conditions, physiological conditions of the phytoplankton etc.. This will be further discussed in the following sections.

Figure 1: Horizontal distribution of MERIS FLH (reflectance units, sr^{-1}) in Skagerrak for the eight dates used in this study. The white lines indicate the transects of 'Color Festival' for each day individually. White areas are clouds, grey are land, and purple are very low values or not processed pixels.

Along the ship transect the correlation between FLH and Chl-*a* was investigated with regards to MERIS L2 confidence and science flags that could influence the validity of the generated FLH product, according to Table 2 [Envisat-1 products specification, volume 11: MERIS products specifications, A. Pellegrini, 2003]. The L2 flags along each transect are shown in Appendix 2.

Name	Description
<i>Pixel Classification</i>	
LAND	Land
CLOUD	Clouds
WATER	Water
<i>Product Confidence Flags</i>	
PCD_1_13	Reflectances
PCD_15	Algal 1
PCD_17	Algal 2
<i>Science Flags</i>	
CASE2_S	Case 2 water
CASE2_ANOM	Anomalous scattering
CASE2_Y	Yellow substance loaded water
ICE_HAZE	Ice or haze
MEDIUM_GLINT	Glint correction turned on
HIGH_GLINT	Uncorrectable glint

Table 2: An extract of the MERIS Confidence and science flags presented for the in this report analyzed transects. These flag values are plotted in Annex 2 for all studied transects.

Figure 2: MERIS FLH (red dots), Algal 1 (blue dots), and Algal 2 (green dots) products, and SOOP Chlorophyll a concentration (yellow circles) and night time in vivo fluorescence (black line) along the ship transects for the various dates. Y-axis on the left hand side correspond to units of Chl [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$], while the y-axis on the right hand side represents FLH [reflectance].

In general, it is found that the agreement between satellite products (Algal 1, Algal 2, FLH) and *in situ* Chl-a is reduced north of 59.0°N , i.e. in the Oslofjord area (Figure 2). This disagreement is expected since this area is very close to land. The satellite ocean products are therefore often heavily contaminated by influence from the atmospheric signal and from partial land/water pixels. As a consequence data sampled north of 59.0°N are not included in the analyses presented in section 3.3. For some of the situations the FLH signal resolve the phytoplankton distribution better than the Algal 1 and Algal 2 products (e.g. February 24th, March 9th and 13th 2003, but for one situation the FLH deviates significantly from the other algal products and the *in vitro* Chl-a (i.e. June 20th 2003). This is probably caused by a failure in the L2 atmospheric correction, which will influence the calculated FLH. This was a situation (June 20th 2003) with an intense bloom of the coccolithophoride *Emiliania huxleyi* and such cases are not well handled by the atmospheric correction, due o its specific impact on the surface light spectra.

3.3. THE FLH:CHL RATIO

The major goal of this study has been to identify a relationship between the remotely sensed FLH and Chl-a as measured *in situ* for our region of interest. Gower et al (1999) present FLH measured by an IOS spectrometer as a linear function of Chl-a for data sampled in British Columbia and in the Baltic. The slope of the function was reported to vary between datasets obtained under different conditions.

However, later (Gower and King, 2003) using FLH generated from MERIS Level 1 data (i.e. TOA radiance) the following relation was suggested:

$$\text{FLH} = k + a \cdot C (1 + 0.2 C)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

where k is the offset, and a is a factor depending on the sun elevation angle (season), fluorescence efficiency and vertical distribution of the phytoplankton in the water column, and instrument bandwidth and spectral location. C is the near-surface chlorophyll concentration (Chl- a). In eq. 1 FLH is not given as a linear function of Chl- a . However, Figure 2 in Gower and King's (2003) article indicates that a linear relationship between FLH and Chl- a may be assumed for values of Chl- a less than $\sim 8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Figure 3 shows the relation between FLH and Chl- a values for the eight dates studied here. Different clustering of data for each individual date is observed. This indicates a wide range of variability in the overall relations between the FLH and the Chl- a . The relations for each individual date range between 1 and 100% in explained variance. In order to increase the confidence in the analysis the MERIS data flagged "invalid" according to the flags for reflectance bands 1-13 (PCD 1-13) are omitted. This reduces the dataset from 56 pairs of satellite and ship observations (Figure 3) to 32 pairs (Figure 4).

Data from latitudes north of 59.0°N are also disregarded in Figure 4. In order to reduce the seasonality in the FLH product the dataset was divided in two. Black diamonds represent data sampled during springtime (February and March) and red squares represent data points sampled during summer time (May and June). Using this seasonal grouping (data from both 2003 and 2004 in each group) a linear regression analysis between FLH and Chl- a was performed. One data point from each cluster (June 20, 2003, sample #1 (southernmost sample), 08:39 UTC and March 9, 2004, sample #2, 09:58 UTC) was disregarded in the statistical analysis due to their mismatch with the remaining data. Both these data points (indicated with a white edge in Figure 4) were sampled close to strong Chl- a gradients and the small delay in the sampling of the water in the Ferrybox system relative to the ship position can explain the difference, in this dynamical active area. The values are associated with station 1 close to the Danish coast. or more likely that the *in vitro* Chl- a collected from the Ferrybox systems at the sampling depth (3-4 m) are not representative for the near surface FLH signal. The dataset from the May-June with high FLH (> 0.001), gives presumable higher FLH:Chl- a ratio, are severely influenced by the data from the Coccolithophore bloom situation on June 20th 2003, as discussed in Section 3.2. Further investigation on the FLH for such conditions must be performed.

Analyzing satellite FLH product obtained under similar conditions (same season of the year, determined by the date of sampling, or e.g. by the concurrent temperature or PAR) allows reaching a level of about 73-75% explained variance in relation to Chl- a measurements. The slope of the linear relation between FLH and Chl- a varies by a factor of five from springtime ($2.0\cdot 10^{-4}$) to summertime ($1.0\cdot 10^{-3}$).

The correlation between FLH:Chl- a and respectively the temperature and PAR is shown in Figure 5. This illustrates further how seasonal variations in the physical conditions influence the fluorescence signal, as also observed in Figure 4. Even though a positive correlation is observed between FLH:Chl- a and temperature, PAR may be the most important factor influencing FLH:Chl ratio. The correlation between FLH:Chl- a and temperature may simply be due to the fact that temperature is highly correlated with PAR, due to the solar heating. Both parameters increase as the sun elevation increases from springtime to summer. The seasonal variation in phytoplankton species composition will also influence the fluorescence efficiency and hence the FLH:Chl- a ratio.

Figure 3: The relation between FLH and in situ Chl-a. The colours represent different dates of sampling, as given in the legend. Only data sampled at latitudes less than 59.0°N are shown. FLH values are averaged over 5 pixels along the transect.

Figure 4: FLH (averaged over 5 pixels along the ship transect) as a function of in situ Chl-a. Red squares indicate data sampled during summer (May-June), while black diamonds indicate data sampled in spring time (February-March). Data are selected from latitudes below 59.0°N, and for pixels where the confidence flag PCD 1-13 (reflectance in bands 1-13) is NOT raised (i.e. value 0). The data points with a white edge were disregarded in the statistical analysis for reasons explained in the text. See also discussion on the dataset from June 20th in Section 3.2.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: FLH:Chl-a ratio as a function of (a) temperature and (b) Photosynthetically available radiation (PAR) for the same data set as presented in Figure 4.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on careful editing and quality control of atmospherically corrected spectral MERIS L2 data has been used to estimate the FLH (Fluorescence Line Height) signal. The FLH was compared with *in situ* observations and a linear relationship is found with an explained variance of about 75%, based on the eight days of observations obtained in 2003 and 2004. The slope of this function is identified to be season/species-specific, and is positively correlated with both PAR and surface water temperature as indicator for the seasonal changes in our waters. These results rely on high quality and editing of the MERIS surface reflectance in the visible spectral range. However, as long as this quality is ensured (by the absence of MERIS L2 confidence flags for reflectance in spectral bands) and the slope of the FLH:Chl-a relation is known, the FLH product could be used to estimate the phytoplankton concentration from MERIS ocean color data. This result also applies in areas where the standard ESA MERIS Algal-1 and Algal-2 products may not be valid. However, also spurious data has been identified and the quality control of the results remains crucial. Specially, during blooms of algae with high scattering (Coccolithophorids) the FLH:Chl-a ratio was found to be high.

Further investigation on the FLH relation during must be performed, but the examples analyzed demonstrate the potential that the FLH data to qualitatively be used in the interpretation of an algal bloom situation. Use of the FLH data together with the other information can reduce the number of false alarms of phytoplankton blooms from erroneously high Chl-*a* values obtained from the Algal-1 product. The FLH product is therefore an important additional source of information to improve the quantitative assessments in algae bloom detection and monitoring. Further work may include a more systematic study of how the accuracy of the MERIS FLH product is influenced by the atmospheric correction. This may be done through studies of FLH generated from concurrent MERIS L1 and L2 data, and *in situ* data. Additional seasonal and inter-annual validation data is also needed to demonstrate the more general robustness of the FLH method, which also includes a better understanding of the phytoplankton fluorescence mechanisms.

5. REFERENCES

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Appendix 1 Maps of MERIS Algal 1, Algal 2, and FLH products

March 28, 2003 (20030328)

May 22, 2003 (20030522)

The MERIS L2 flag indicator for validity of the product. Black indicates invalid pixels

June 6, 2003 (20030606)

The MERIS L2 flag indicator for validity of the product. Black indicates invalid pixels

June 20, 2003 (20030620)

The MERIS L2 flag indicator for validity of the product. Black indicates invalid pixels

February 24, 2004 (20040224)

The MERIS L2 flag indicator for validity of the product. Black indicates invalid pixels

March 9, 2004 (20040309)

June 29, 2004 (20040629)

The MERIS L2 flag indicator for validity of the product. Black indicates invalid pixels

Appendix 2 MERIS L2 confidence and science flags along 'Color Festival' transect for each date

Figure A2-1: MERIS Case 1 and Case 2 water Chl-a (Algal 1, and Algal 2, respectively), and FLH products along the SOOP transect on March 28, 2003. Below are shown the values (0/1) of relevant MERIS L2 flags along the same transect. The y-axes in the L2 flag windows are dimensionless

Figure A2-2: MERIS Case 1 and Case 2 water Chl-a (Algal 1, and Algal 2, respectively), and FLH products along the SOOP transect on May 22, 2003. Below are shown the values (0/1) of relevant MERIS L2 flags along the same transect. The y-axes in the L2 flag windows are dimensionless

Figure A2-3: MERIS Case 1 and Case 2 water Chl-a (Algal 1, and Algal 2, respectively), and FLH products along the SOOP transect on June 6, 2003. Below are shown the values (0/1) of relevant MERIS L2 flags along the same transect. The y-axis in the L2 flag windows are dimensionless

Figure A2-4: MERIS Case 1 and Case 2 water Chl-a (Algal 1, and Algal 2, respectively), and FLH products along the SOOP transect on June 20, 2003. Below are shown the values (0/1) of relevant MERIS L2 flags along the same transect. The y-axes in the L2 flag windows are dimensionless

Figure A2-5: MERIS Case 1 and Case 2 water Chl-a (Algal 1, and Algal 2, respectively), and FLH products along the SOOP transect on February 24, 2004. Below are shown the values (0/1) of relevant MERIS L2 flags along the same transect. The y-axes in the L2 flag windows are dimensionless

Figure A2-6: MERIS Case 1 and Case 2 water Chl-a (Algal 1, and Algal 2, respectively), and FLH products along the SOOP transect on March 9, 2004. Below are shown the values (0/1) of relevant MERIS L2 flags along the same transect. The y-axes in the L2 flag windows are dimensionless

Figure A2-7: MERIS Case 1 and Case 2 water Chl-a (Algal 1, and Algal 2, respectively), and FLH products along the SOOP transect on March 16, 2004. Below are shown the values (0/1) of relevant MERIS L2 flags along the same transect. The y-axes in the L2 flag windows are dimensionless

Figure A2-8: MERIS Case 1 and Case 2 water Chl-a (Algal 1, and Algal 2, respectively), and FLH products along the SOOP transect on June 29, 2004. Below are shown the values (0/1) of relevant MERIS L2 flags along the same transect. The y-axes in the L2 flag windows are dimensionless

